

Basic Axiomatic Particle with CPT conservation

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Abstract

Currently defined basic particles of the physical universe can be explained in axiomatic form following CPT conservation.

1 Introduction

The current known forces of a universe consist of four kinds – Gravity, electromagnetism, strong, and weak forces[1]. These interactions, in turn, form an amount of energy. There are two kinds of energy status. One is potential energy, and the other is kinetic energy. If one is to simulate the universe, it would be of the basic four forces and energies that consist current universe.

Beyond this fact, there are constituents called “matter”. In state-of-the-art physics, “matter” is about the attribute that the basic particle forms (especially what is called “spin” – the angular momentum of the particle). And thus, through simulating particles, simulating the general universe could be reached.

Previously, from what has been discussed, basic axioms from game theory and the conservation of CPT asymmetry could be derived. Then, as an actual implementation, how could it be realized as a procedural architecture?

2 Following CPT conservation

As in the preceding discussion, every energy has general options to be a particle. As one can misunderstand that particle means only “matter”, but the basic particles that are defined in physics have a broader meaning containing what is to be before energy and matter.

Every particle has an option to have a mass. This means that there is no particle without a mass attribute. On the other hand, every particle also has an option to have a charge. This also means that there is no particle without a charge attribute. Although both mass and charge could be 0, it doesn't mean that they are free from total conservation of energy (including energy-mass equivalence relation) in the universe.

2.1 Step 1. Spontaneous Higgs asymmetry

The mechanism introducing a mass attribute to the universe is called spontaneous symmetry breaking of Higgs Boson particle[2]. And yet, as one can see the word ‘spontaneous’ in the phenomenon, the reason why this happens is to be investigated. But as for default in forming axioms of the universe that could be simulated, it would not be an exception to the basic rule of conservation in CPT symmetry. So, let's put this not in the area of why, but regard it as a technique in maintaining the concurrent temporal flow.

2.2 Step 2. Gravity and Electromagnetism asymmetry

Maxwell's equation introduces us to the relation between mass and electromagnetism. Although the equation is about electricity and magnetism, on a particle scale, electromagnetism and gravity are the only two basic attributes discussed before.

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$$F_e + F_m = q(E + \vec{v} \times B)$$

It is often regarded that gravity comes from a mass attribute and depends on mass. But at least for simulation, mass and gravity just fits in the step of checking mass-energy equivalence. Without this premise, object that has an attribute of infinite gravity like black-hole contradicts the whole energy equation of observable universe. If there is time frame to regard infinite gravity, on the other hand, there is time frame to regard the finite energy from the given source. And by this premise, electromagnetism and gravity could be differentiated by their kinetic attribute – called as ‘spin’.

By the mass-energy equivalence equation, every matter can be translated into a form of energy. And by mean of form of energy, particle that has a charge forms electromagnetism. So this could be understood like this (q is charge in ratio with electron.):

$$E = E_{gravity} \times E_{electromagnetism} = E_{gravity} + E_{electromagnetism} = q(F_{mass} + \vec{S} \times (F_{charge}))$$

By definition, $E_{electromagnetism}$ is potential energy from electromagnetism of matter, force about mass($q \cdot F_{mass}$) would be of gravity and \vec{S} is spin. It is noticeable that given mass with charge without spin forms energy-mass equivalence equation. And it is important to say that basic unit of charge – electron decays into two photons.

2.3 Step 3. Strong and weak asymmetry

Furthermore, beyond gravity and electromagnetism, there are strong and weak forces. These two forces interact in relatively short distance than the gravity and electromagnetism. Although strong and weak forces are basically about attraction and repulsion between particles, they differ with gravity and electromagnetism in the context of stabilizing the correct charge of particle. Gravity and electromagnetism forces have no restriction in amount of given charge, but strong and weak forces have restriction to match correct amount of charge in preset while configuring total charge when combining with the others.

And this leads to the phenomenon in strong and weak asymmetry. While keeping symmetry, the difference between cross product of gravity and electromagnetism unit and sum of the gravity and electromagnetism is essential. And to keep symmetry mentioned earlier as premises, this leads to the asymmetrical moment of strong and weak force.

$$(E_{gravity} + E_{electromagnetism}) - E_{gravity} \times E_{electromagnetism} = \Delta E_{strong} + \Delta E_{weak}$$

Then, how’s the amount of ratio gets between strong and weak? There could be many explanations, but as discussed previously, it would depend on whether the particle has the correct amount of charge in preset. If amount of charge fits in total, ΔE_{strong} would get relatively stabilized and left over ΔE_{weak} would be in stabilization form in total, too. But in the other cases, E_{strong} and E_{weak} would unbalance so that amount of asymmetry would be in control.

2.4 Step 4. Temporal asymmetry

While calculating asymmetrical moments till here, CP-related attributes have been kept. But meanwhile, equivalence in total energy has been shook and needs to be corrected in symmetry. This causes left over or lack of energy in sum total. Then, with the final choice, it could be preserved through the temporal attribute.

There can be two kinds of flows in temporal symmetry. One is to keep it in its original turn – order by order, and the other is to keep it by the original sum.

3 Following Basic Particles

Then what is a main factor that decides the types of basic particle? As discussed, it would be from the default attributes of mass and charge, and the step where CPT asymmetry fulfills.

3.1 Type 1. Scalar Boson

Scalar boson is a particle that exists without any conditions of CPT asymmetry. This is because the attribute of mass always exists in any particle without any additional options.

Continuing from previously discussed, Higgs mechanism is mediated by Higgs Boson.

3.2 Type 2. Gauge Boson

Gauge boson is a particle that exists within at least condition of C-asymmetry. This is because the mass-energy equivalence applies throughout any asymmetries of P and T.

3.3 Type 3. Lepton Fermion

Lepton Fermion is a particle that exists within at least condition of CP-asymmetry. This is because the weak force which makes countable attributes in relation with the other particles must have an measurable order mathematically. Especially by differentiating Boson (follows Bose-Einstein statistics) and Fermion (follows Fermi-Dirac statistics), boundaries from energy density to each matter is created. So, it correlates with ordinal within set theory.

3.4 Type 4. Quark Fermion

Quark Fermion is a particle that exists within the full condition of CPT-asymmetry. This is because the left over (or lack) within interactions must be conserved throughout in space and time by anyway.

Why does spin of Boson try to complete in full integer form and Fermion in half? There could be many explanations. But the reasonable way to understand this phenomenon is that energy is universal in comparison to the way matter exists. At first, mass and charge was just set to ‘exist’ without any reason. But by introducing asymmetry between strong and weak force to complete symmetry by full CPT condition, the specificity for completion in any asymmetrical particle emerges.

But then, why does it has to be in a unit of one and of a half? It’s because the nature of spin forms a consistency in the asymmetry itself. As previously discussed[3]:

$$E = LFO \cdot \sum_t^{\forall} TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E)) \cdot (1 - ME(E)) \cdot (1 - OE(E)) + \left(\sum_t^{\forall} SR_t \sin a_t - \sum_t^{\forall} CR_t \sin b_t \right)$$

As like in equation, spin forms a shooting angle from time to time. For example, assuming $1 - OE(E)$ to be in exact 1/2 makes $1 - ME(E)$ to be in exact 1/2, also. And as $1 - PE(E)$ is a correction from partial to the whole in any kinetic form, $LFO \cdot (1 - PE(E))$ converges to 1. This $1/4 \cdot TEO$ makes the need for conservation of left over of $3/4 \cdot TEO$.

At that t , $CR_t \sin b_t$ would conserve the left over, and in another t' or so, $SR_{t'} \sin a_{t'}$ would partially be an offset. In this sense, as for Fermions, $\sin a_t$ and $\sin b_t$ gets limit in half assuming situation without further bias. This makes any asymmetry to be resolved at least more than one time step. On the other hand, as for Bosons, any asymmetry could be resolved by a single time step. This creates the binary state in existence of matter – exists or not.

4 Following Asymmetries in Particles

4.1 Why Should the Space’s Maximal Dimension be 3?

Previously, what has been discussed for asymmetries are about Searching for Reality and Concealment of Reality. The relations of two could be expanded by the formation of biases – Perception Error(PE), Memory Error(ME), and Opportunity Error(OE) in Table 1.

Table 1 to following equation:

Table 1: Asymmetry-Error relations

		Optimal t	With PE	With ME	With OE
Original	(Expectation)	E	Not specific	Not specific	Not specific
Type 1	SR=CR	In symmetry	T asymmetry	Not specific	Not specific
Type 2	SR-CR > 0	PT asymmetry	PT asymmetry	PT asymmetry	Not specific
Type 3	CR-SR > 0	CPT asymmetry	CPT asymmetry	CPT asymmetry	CPT asymmetry

$$\begin{aligned}
TEO &= \text{Expected } E = E_{T_{ype1}} + E_{T_{ype2}} + E_{T_{ype3}} \\
\Rightarrow E_{T_{ype1}} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E)), \\
E_{T_{ype2}} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E)) + \sum SR - \sum CR, \\
E_{T_{ype3}} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - OE(E)) + \sum SR - \sum CR \\
\Rightarrow \text{Expected } E &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot ((1 - PE(E)) \\
&\quad + (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E)) + (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - OE(E)))
\end{aligned}$$

Let's assume that $\alpha = 1 - PE(E)$, $\beta = 1 - ME(E)$, and $\gamma = 1 - OE(E)$:

$$LFO \cdot (\alpha + \alpha\beta + \alpha\beta\gamma) = E, \alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$$

And by definition of PE within the same energy:

$$1 - \alpha = LFO$$

And the atomic energy distribution form could be driven as:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\beta + \gamma)\alpha(1 + \beta + \beta\gamma) &= 1 \\
\Rightarrow 1 + \beta + \beta\gamma &= \frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma)\alpha} \\
\Rightarrow 1 &= \frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma)\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{\beta} - \gamma \\
\gamma &= \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma)} - 1 \right) - 1
\end{aligned}$$

This formation could be a form of emission of dimensionality, understanding the photon(light).

4.2 Mode of Observations

The result from Einstein field equation affecting energy expression implies amount of energy that added as electromagnetic gravitational energy causes not only spin of particle to be in specific boundary, but also boundary phase of energy that interacts with.

As ordered in fermion spin, matter has distribution of Fermi-Dirac statistics.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Assuming that, } \sum_i \bar{n}_i &= N \\
\Rightarrow \bar{n}(\varepsilon_i) = g_i \bar{n}_i &= \frac{g_i}{e^{(\varepsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T} + 1} \\
\sum_i \bar{n}(\varepsilon_i) &= E
\end{aligned}$$

where κ_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, ε_i is the energy of the single-particle state i , and μ is the total chemical potential [4]. And sum by all states of single-particle, the distribution normalizes.

There are three known ways to explain ensembles resulting in phase state. Grand-canonical, canonical, micro-canonical each has their own relation with describing ensemble.

Grand-canonical ensemble describes itself by the equation of its own by expectation in given energy within law of conservation.

Canonical ensemble describes itself by chaining free energy given by the sum of other ensembles of energy states, which resembles with preceding discussion of Einstein field equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_i(N - n_i) &\equiv \sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots}^{(i)} e^{-\beta(n_1 \varepsilon_1 + n_2 \varepsilon_2 + \dots)} \\
\Rightarrow \bar{n}_i &= \frac{\sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots} n_i e^{-\beta(n_1 \varepsilon_1 + n_2 \varepsilon_2 + \dots + n_i \varepsilon_i + \dots)}}{\sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots} e^{-\beta(n_1 \varepsilon_1 + n_2 \varepsilon_2 + \dots + n_i \varepsilon_i + \dots)}} = \frac{1}{[Z_i(N)/Z_i(N-1)] e^{\beta \varepsilon_i} + 1} \\
&= \frac{1}{e^{(\varepsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T} + 1} \left(\Rightarrow e^{\varepsilon_i - \mu} = \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right)^{\kappa_B T} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Micro-canonical ensemble describes itself by Lagrange multipliers α, β [4]:

$$\begin{aligned}
W &= \prod_i w(n_i, g_i) = \prod_i \frac{g_i!}{n_i! (g_i - n_i)!} \\
\Rightarrow f(n_i) &= \ln(W) + \alpha \left(N - \sum n_i \right) + \beta \left(E - \sum n_i \varepsilon_i \right) \\
\Rightarrow (\text{By Stirling's approximation}) &n_i = \arg \max_{n_i} f(n_i) = \frac{g_i}{e^{\alpha + \beta \varepsilon_i} + 1}
\end{aligned}$$

where W is the number of ways that total of particles can be classified into energy levels according to their energies [5] with a fixed number of particle N and a fixed energy E .

So, it would be natural to say that at least both Einstein field equation and conservation of CPT affect phase transition. If then, the model could be rearranged by maximal consideration within given concepts from Fermi-Dirac statistics.

The two perspectives are each related with theory of relativity and CPT conservation. Then why does summation of series product in power of e corresponds to LFO ? And why does maximized number of ways in combination of particle corresponds to conservation in SR and CR ?

By terms of LFO and conservation in SR and CR , assuming that canonical and micro-canonical ensemble has equal conclusion:

$$\begin{aligned}
(LFO \text{ Chain}) &\equiv (CPT \text{ Conservation}) \\
\Rightarrow Z_i(N)/Z_i(N-1) &= e^{-\mu/k_B T} = \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} - \frac{1}{e^{\mu/k_B T}} + 1 &= 1 \\
\Rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{(\varepsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T}} - 1 + e^{\mu/k_B T} &= e^{\mu/k_B T} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} + 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/k_B T}} - 1 &= e^{\mu/k_B T} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\varepsilon_i/k_B T}} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/k_B T}} - 1 &= -e^{\mu/k_B T}
\end{aligned}$$

Again, from what has been discussed:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{1}{(\beta + \gamma)} - 1 \right) - 1$$

Note that $e^{i\pi}$ forms a projection in complex plain. And the α , β , and γ is in a form of probability. By the upper equation, the mean of ensemble is to be a probability in their atomic particle level. Fermi-Dirac's number of cases in such expression within complex plain is summarized into an observation of minimal probability size within α , β , and γ .

Then how could this be a form of dimensionality? If assuming that the '-1' term that appears after every calculation serves as a photon in atomic emission, it would be of alpha, beta, and gamma ray.

Again, the definition of energy in frequency follows:

$$E = \hbar v \quad (v = \frac{c}{\lambda})$$

The possibles form in matter particle in given state is number of cases within given kinetic energy, and this brings to the matter of observation. Assuming that $\sum E$ is TEO :

$$LFO \cdot \sum E \cdot (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - OE(E)) + \sum SR - \sum CR = \hbar v$$

To get $\sum E$ with $LFO = 1$ in its full form:

$$\sum E\alpha + \sum E\alpha\beta + \sum E\alpha\beta\gamma = \hbar v$$

If assuming exact observation by $\alpha \approx 1$ and $\gamma \approx 1 - \beta$:

$$\sum E\beta(2 - \beta) = 0 \Rightarrow \|\beta\| \approx 0 \text{ or } 2$$

In other case, assuming exact observation by $\alpha \approx 1$ and $\beta \approx 1 - \gamma$:

$$\sum E(1 + \gamma)(1 - \gamma) = 0 \Rightarrow \|\gamma\| \approx 1$$

As last case, assuming without restriction in LFO and exact observation by $\beta = 1$ and $\gamma = 1$:

$$3 \sum E\alpha = \hbar v \Rightarrow \|\alpha\| \approx \frac{1}{3}$$

(Note that α , β , and γ could be in the form of vector in complex plain.)

These give a view that there could be four different modes of exact interaction(observation). First, it is by complete observation without any bias. And second, it is the observation from fixed Memory Error(ME) – underestimation. And third, it is the observation from Opportunity Error(OE) – overestimation. And last, it is the observation from Perception Error(PE) – non-equivalent from partial to the whole. As seen, the exact interaction probability by its nature of observation changes. And it constitutes the possible kinds of interaction – by energy or matter.

4.3 Phase Transition of Energy-Matter

In this part, four branches of proton-proton process would be discussed. Every atom has two modes – fusion or fission.

Basically, energy by nuclear is a heat. Heat is about the number of cases in energy which could be transferred to another energy. And by the possible suggestion, because four types of energy is correlated in this equation (without any unit notation):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assuming that, } E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{Gravity}} = E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}} \models \\
& \text{(Eqn. 1) } E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} = \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Gravity}}} \\
& \text{(Eqn. 2) } E_{\text{Gravity}} = \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Electromagnetism}}} \\
& \text{(Eqn. 3) } E_{\text{Weak}} = E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{Gravity}} - E_{\text{Strong}} \\
& \text{(Eqn. 4) } E_{\text{Strong}} = E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{Gravity}} - E_{\text{Weak}}
\end{aligned}$$

And the potential of gravity and electromagnetism energy takes a form of pair annihilation, followed by equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assuming that, Time } \forall^3 t, CR_t < SR_t \\
& \left(-1 \leq \frac{SR_t - CR_t}{TEO^3} < \frac{1}{TEO^2} \right) \models E_{\text{Gravity}} = \frac{SR_t - CR_t}{TEO^3} \\
& \text{Assuming that, Time } \forall^3 t, CR_t > SR_t \\
& \left(-\frac{1}{TEO^2} < \frac{CR_t - SR_t}{TEO^3} \leq 1 \right) \models E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} = \frac{CR_t - SR_t}{TEO^3} \\
& \Rightarrow -2 \leq e^- + e^+ < 1 \quad (\because CR_t - SR_t \leq TEO)
\end{aligned}$$

By the upper discussion, adding electron and positron causes another two unit minimal state to overcome reality as an energy. This could be explained in two possible ways.

One is to leave two hydrogen ions (Eqn. 1, p-p I branch). By creating two minus unit charge in interaction, conservation in CPT has to bring additional two plus charge in minimal. This creates the opportunity of consolidation in two hydrogen atoms.

And the other is to leave two electrons which in conclusion turns a hydrogen ion to a helium ion and leaves behind gamma ray as electron (Eqn. 2, p-p II branch). By approaching maximal one plus unit charge in potential, this causes emission within gamma ray and the consecutive left-over energy in conservation.

Next, reaction by strong and weak energy occurs. This happens in two ways.

By strong energy, it adds one proton to nuclear and leaves behind one positron and one neutron (Eqn. 3, p-p III branch). It could be suggested as by potentiating strong energy to emit neutron ray, one positron could be derived.

By weak energy, it adds one proton to existing helium-3 (${}^3\text{He}$) and leaves behind one positron and a neutron (Eqn. 4, p-p IV branch). It could be suggested as by potentiating weak energy to emit neutron ray, two atoms fuse by their pulling energy and one positron could be derived.

The possible main difference in III and IV branch is that the initial difference in one proton of $\frac{3}{2}He$ and $\frac{1}{2}H$ - by which a proton fills asymmetry of charge in IV branch and induces fluctuation of weak force.

4.4 Unification of energies

So, these four nuclear modes conserve total amount of energy in sum total within interaction. And the equation goes like:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assuming that, } |E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{Gravity}}| \leq \cos \theta \\
& \Rightarrow E = E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{gravity}} + E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}} \\
& = E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} + E_{\text{gravity}} + E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}} \\
& \Rightarrow \text{Electromagnetism Gravitational Field by } \mathcal{B} = \{2, -2, 2i, -2i\} \Rightarrow \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle = \text{Group } G(\cdot) \\
& \Rightarrow E = \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Gravity}}} + \frac{E_{\text{Weak}} + E_{\text{Strong}}}{E_{\text{Electromagnetism}}} + 2 \cdot E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \cdot E_{\text{Gravity}} - E_{\text{Strong}} - E_{\text{Weak}} \\
& = (E_{\text{Strong}} + E_{\text{Weak}}) \times \left(\frac{1}{E_{\text{Gravity}}} + \frac{1}{E_{\text{Electromagnetism}}} - 1 \right) + 2 \times E_{\text{Electromagnetism}} \times E_{\text{Gravity}}
\end{aligned}$$

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